

Fig. 1. Diffractogram.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA OF THE COMPLEX

Peak no.	d Spacing Å	Relative intensity $\times 100 I/I_0$	Observed $\sin^2 \theta$	Calcd. $\sin^2 \theta$	(hkl)
1	8.757 7	100 0	0.007 7	0.007 7	(110)
2	6.468 4	22.5	0.014 2	0.014 2	(002)
3	5.039 0	95.6	0.023 4	0.022 9	(211)
4	4.358 5	89.5	0.031 96	0.030 99	(220)
				0.032 0	(008)
5	3.951 5	48.3	0.038 06	0.038 4	(301)
				0.038 7	(310)
6	3.547 7	60.9	0.047 2	0.047 5	(203)
7	3.266 6	18.6	0.055 7	0.056 9	(004)
8	3.099 8	17.6	0.061 8	0.061 9	(400)
9	2.857 7	7.5	0.072 8	0.073 8	(331)
10	2.722 3	11.9	0.080 2	0.081 0	(421)
11	2.629 2	3.4	0.085 9	0.083 9	(332)
				0.087 8	(224)
12	2.483 0	20.0	0.096 0	0.096 8	(500)
13	2.404 4	4.5	0.102 7	0.104 3	(205)
				0.107 4	(333)
14	2.320 8	6.7	0.110 3	0.109 5	(423)
				0.111 1	(502)
15	2.237 8	14.7	0.118 6	0.119 8	(225)
				0.118 8	(404)
16	1.972 9	5.5	0.152 7	0.153 7	(504)
				0.150 9	(405)
17	1.884 2	8.8	0.167 4	0.169 2	(524)
				0.166 7	(316)
18	1.752 3	8.2	0.193 5	0.193 7	(710)
				0.193 4	(701)

$A=0.0038742$, $a=12.3^{\circ}53 \text{ \AA}$, $C=0.0035563$, $c=12.9269 \text{ \AA}$, cell volume = $1982.980 \text{ \AA}^3$, mol. wt. = 522.55, density (calcd) = 1.7711 g cm^{-3} ($n=4$), density (obs) = 1.8232 g cm^{-3} .

value of density of the complex has been found to be 1.8232 g cm^{-3} which is fairly in good agreement within the limits of the experimental error.

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References

1. A. B. KHARE, R. K. GAUTAM and O. P. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 660.
2. N. F. M. HENRY, H. LIPSON and W. A. WOOSTER, "Interpretation of X-ray Diffraction Photographs", London, McMillan, p. 128.
3. M. J. BURGER, "X-ray Crystallography", Wiley, New York, 1953, p. 100.
4. H. S. PETER, H. P. ROOKSBY and A. J. C. WILSON, "X-ray Diffraction by Polycrystalline Materials", Institute of Physics, London 1955, p. 344.
5. M. M. WOOLFSON, "An Introduction to X-ray Crystallography", Cambridge University Press, 1980, p. 125.

Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes of Schiff Bases derived from Amino-thiazole

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In this paper we report the isolation and characterisation of four new terdentate Schiff base ligands derived from 4-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazole and substituted-salicylaldehyde (5-methyl (A), 5-chloro (B), 5-bromo (C)) or β -hydroxynaphthaldehyde (D) and their complexes with Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} .

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Experimental

Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of equimolar quantities of a substituted-salicylaldehyde or β -hydroxy- α -naphthaldehyde and 4-(*p*-ethoxy)phenyl-2-aminothiazole in ethanolic medium¹. Compounds separated on cooling the solution were recrystallised from ethanol and dried under vacuum. Elemental analyses and molecular weight data are given in Table 1. Physical measurements were carried out as described in our earlier report².

250°. These were soluble in benzene, chloroform and nitrobenzene. Cu^{II} complexes were olive-green and Zn^{II} complexes were orange-red in colour. Elemental analyses indicated 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry and their monomeric nature was confirmed from the molecular weight determination. Very low electrical conductivity in nitrobenzene solutions indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

Electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes exhibited two bands at ~15 000 and ~26 000 cm⁻¹. A broad

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE SCHIFF BASES AND Cu^{II} AND Zn^{II} COMPLEXES

Aldehyde	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/Calcd					M	Mol. weight
		C	H	N	S			
A	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	67.80 (67.45)	5.40 (5.32)	8.40 (8.28)	9.50 (9.46)	—	980 (938)	
	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S) ₂	61.80 (61.67)	4.51 (4.60)	7.60 (7.57)	8.88 (8.65)	8.69 (8.84)	708 (739)	
	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S) ₂	61.70 (61.88)	4.50 (4.61)	7.69 (7.59)	8.80 (8.67)	8.48 (8.61)	700 (737)	
B	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ SCl	60.18 (60.25)	4.29 (4.18)	7.60 (7.81)	8.80 (8.92)	—	840 (868)	
	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ SCl) ₂	55.20 (55.36)	3.68 (3.58)	7.00 (7.17)	8.28 (8.20)	8.30 (8.88)	740 (780)	
	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ SCl) ₂	55.30 (55.49)	3.48 (3.59)	7.00 (7.19)	8.31 (8.22)	8.08 (8.15)	750 (778)	
C	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ SBr	58.63 (58.59)	3.60 (3.72)	6.81 (6.74)	7.60 (7.94)	—	889 (403)	
	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ SBr) ₂	49.85 (49.69)	3.10 (3.22)	6.58 (6.44)	7.29 (7.36)	7.80 (7.52)	830 (869)	
	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ SBr) ₂	49.90 (49.79)	3.30 (3.22)	6.40 (6.45)	7.43 (7.37)	7.20 (7.32)	849 (867)	
D	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	70.50 (70.58)	4.63 (4.81)	7.36 (7.48)	8.68 (8.55)	—	939 (974)	
	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S) ₂	65.20 (65.97)	4.03 (4.19)	6.80 (6.90)	7.79 (7.88)	8.19 (8.06)	780 (811)	
	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S) ₂	65.10 (65.22)	4.10 (4.26)	6.73 (6.91)	7.99 (7.90)	7.68 (7.84)	780 (809)	

Results and Discussion

Schiff bases : All Schiff bases were crystalline yellow solids having sharp melting points and were soluble in benzene, acetone and carbon tetrachloride. 2-Aminothiazole showed absorption band at 275 nm while the other aromatic amino compounds with comparable structures absorb at ~300 nm^{3,4}. Schiff bases reported have shown electronic absorption band at ~400 nm. The shift of the band to higher wavelength may be due to extended conjugation in the molecules⁵. A weak and broad band ~2900 cm⁻¹ instead of a strong one at ~3100 cm⁻¹ (expected for phenolic free OH) was observed for these ligands. This shift may be due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the azomethine group, forming a stable six-membered ring⁶. ν_{C-O} and $\nu_{C=N}$ modes were observed at ~1280 and ~1630 cm⁻¹ respectively, and are in agreement with the earlier reported data⁶.

Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes : All complexes were crystalline solids melting with decomposition above

unsymmetric band at ~15 000 cm⁻¹ may be due to ²T_{2g} ← ²E_g transition in octahedral geometry. A band of high intensity at ~26 000 cm⁻¹ may be due to ligand-metal charge transfer. Magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} complexes were around 1.9 B.M. Electronic spectra along with magnetic susceptibility data suggest a distorted octahedral geometry for Cu^{II} complexes.

Electronic spectra of Zn^{II} complexes exhibit a sharp band of high intensity at ~26 000 cm⁻¹ and it may be due to ligand-metal charge transfer. The absence of ν_{OH} band in the complexes indicated that OH group proton is used in M-O bond formation⁶. ν_{C-O} bands for the complexes were observed at ~1330 cm⁻¹ as against ~1280 cm⁻¹ for the ligand, and $\nu_{C=N}$ mode at ~1580 cm⁻¹ as against ~1630 cm⁻¹ for the ligands. Such shift of ν_{C-O} towards higher frequency and lowering of $\nu_{C=N}$ in the complexes suggested coordination through oxygen of the phenolic group and nitrogen of the azomethine group⁶. The 520-560 cm⁻¹ band in the Cu^{II} complexes were assigned to the ν_{Cu-N} mode and the 310 cm⁻¹ band to $\nu_{Cu-O}+$

$\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ frequency^{9,10}. The presence of broad and weak non-ligand band at 310–370 cm^{-1} in the Zn^{II} complexes may be due to $\nu_{\text{Zn-N}}$ mode^{11,12}.

References

1. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longman, London, 1969, p. 653.
2. C. K. BHASKARR and P. G. MORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 270
3. R. A. MATHES and J. T. GREGORY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3867.
4. L. H. CONOVER and D. S. TARBELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5221.
5. S. PATAI, "The Chemistry of the Carbon-Nitrogen Double Bond", Interscience, London, 1970, p. 181.
6. J. E. KOVACIC, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1967, **23**, 183.
7. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Interscience, New York, 1966, p. 218.
8. L. SACCONI, M. GIAMPOLINI and V. CAMPIGLI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 407.
9. D. M. ADAMS, "Metal Ligand and Related Vibrations", Edward Arnold, London, 1967, p. 310.
10. R. A. CONDRATE and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 2590.
11. J. F. JACKOWITZ, J. A. DURKIN and J. G. WALTER, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1967, **23**, 67.
12. J. F. JACKOWITZ and J. G. WALTER, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1966, **22**, 1393.

Study of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with Nitrilotriacetic Acid and Salicylidene-2-iminopyridine

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IN this communication, we report the results of our potentiometric investigation on the equilibrium study of ternary complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as the primary ligand (A) and the Schiff base, salicylidene-2-iminopyridine (SAP or HL), as the secondary ligand in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium (ionic strength, $I=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$) and at 30 and 40°.

Experimental

A.R. grade or purified chemicals were used in the study. A 0.02 M solution of salicylidene-2-iminopyridine was made in lime-distilled ethanol. Solutions of the metal nitrates (0.01 M) were made in 0.1 M HNO_3 . Nitrilotriacetic acid (0.01 M) was used as the trisodium salt. A ECL 5651 digital pH-meter with a combined glass electrode assembly was used. Representative pH-titration curves are shown in Fig. 1.

Practical proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated by Bjerrums method^{3,8} as

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves at 30° in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium ($I=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$): (a) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M SAP + 0.1M KNO_3 , (b) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal nitrate + 0.002M SAP + 0.1M KNO_3 , (c) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M metal nitrate + 0.002M SAP + 0.1M KNO_3 , (d) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M NTA + 0.1M KNO_3 , (e) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal nitrate + 0.1M KNO_3 , and (f) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.1M KNO_3 , titrant, NaOH (0.9861M), initial volume of each solution = 50 ml.

modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴ and others⁵. Duplicate titrations using varying ligand concentrations were performed to ensure the absence of ligand hydrolysis under the experimental condition.

Results and Discussion

In the mixed ligand system it is observed that metal-NTA curve (e) (Fig. 1) departs NTA curve (d) at low pH showing that metal-NTA complex formation takes place at low pH. Metal-NTA complex species occurring at $\text{pH} \approx 4$ is stable even at higher pH values. The mixed ligand titration curve (b) diverges from the secondary ligand titration curve (a) after complete formation of (metal-NTA) complex. It may, therefore, be assumed that the secondary ligand (SAP) would combine with metal-NTA complex species to form the ternary species.

It is evident from Table 1 that lower value of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ than $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$ and $\log K_{\text{ML}_2}^{\text{ML}}$ is attributed to the greater repulsion between NTA^{3-} anion and L^- anion as compared to that between two L^- anions. Such repulsion is however absent in the formation of ML species. Stability of $\text{M}(\text{NTA})(\text{L})$ complexes